

LOTIN TILINING ZAMONAVIY TILLARGA BEVOSITA VA BILVOSITA TA'SIRI

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Annotatsiya: Inson hayoti davomida turli insonlar bilan uchrashadi, turli millat vakillarining urf-odat va tilidagi o'ziga xosliklarga duch keladi. Binobarin, bugungi kunda ilmiy adabiyotlar bilan ishlash jarayonida "olik til" hisoblanmish lotin tilining boshqa tillarda "yashayotganligi"ni ko'p kuzatamiz. Maqolada lotin tilining bugungi kunda zamonaviy tillarga ta'siri haqida so'z boradi. Bu maqolada lotin tilining tarqalishi haqida to'liq to'xtalmadik, ayrim keng tarqalgan terminlar haqida so'z yuritdik, xolos.

Kalit so'zlar: lotin tili, zamonaviy til, chet tili, ona tili, xalqaro til, jahon tili, o'lik til, o'zlashma so'zlar, so'z yasalishi.

DIRECT AND INDIRECT INFLUENCE OF LATIN ON MODERN LANGUAGES

Abstract: During his life, a person meets different people, encounters peculiarities of customs and language of representatives of different nationalities. Therefore, today, in the process of working with scientific literature, we often observe that the Latin language, which is considered a "distant language", "lives" in other languages. The article talks about the influence of Latin on modern languages today. In this article, we did not dwell on the spread of the Latin language, we only talked about some common terms.

Keywords: Latin language, modern language, foreign language, mother tongue, international language, world language, dead language, borrowed words, word formation.

ПРЯМОЕ И КОСВЕННОЕ ВЛИЯНИЕ ЛАТЫНИ НА СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ЯЗЫКИ

Аннотация: В течение своей жизни человек встречается разных людей, сталкивается с особенностями обычаев и языка представителей разных национальностей. Поэтому сегодня в процессе работы с научной литературой мы часто наблюдаем, что латинский язык, считающийся «дальним языком», «живет» в других языках. В статье говорится о влиянии латыни на современные языки сегодня. В этой статье мы не стали останавливаться на распространении латинского языка, а лишь рассказали о некоторых общеупотребительных терминах.

Ключевые слова: латинский язык, современный язык, иностранный язык, родной язык, интернациональный язык, мировой язык, мертвый язык, заимствованные слова, словообразование.

KIRISH

Hozirgi zamon pedagogikasi chet tili fanining maktablarda va oliy o'quv yurtlarida o'quvchi va studentlarni har tomonlama rivojlantiruvchi o'quv fani sifatida e'tirof etmoqda. Jamiyatshunos va psixolog olimlar bironta chet tilini o'rganishning ahamiyatini alohida ta'kidlab unga jamiyatdagi ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, ilmiy-texnikaviy taraqqiyotning harakatlantiruvchi omili sifatida baho bermoqdalar. Maqsad, bo'lajak mutaxassislarimiz dunyoning u yoki bu mamlakatiga borganda ularning tillarida gapira bilishlaridir. Biz ushbu maqolada tibbiyot muassasalarida ta'lim

olayotgan yoshlarimizning chet (ingliz, nemis, frantsuz) tillarini amaliy jihatdan egallashlaridagi qiyinchiliklarni bartaraf etish haqida fikr yuritamiz.

MA'LUMOTLAR VA USLUBLAR

Lotin tili qadimdan tibbiyot fanlari tili bo'lgan. Qadimgi dunyo faylasuflari, tabiblari va notiqalari lotin tilidan xalqaro so'zlashuv vositasi - tili sifatida foydalanishgan. Lotin tili hozirgi kunda o'lik til hisoblansada, butun dunyo tibbiyot sohasida ishlayotgan mutaxassislar uchun eng qulay til bo'lib qolmoqda. Butunjahon tibbiyot terminologiyasi shu tilga asoslangan. Zamonaviy shifokor lotin tilini mukammal bilmog'i shart va zarur. Nima uchun?

Birinchidan, tibbiyotni yaxshi o'zlashtirish va tushinish uchun.

Ikkinchidan, bemorlar orasida kelib chiqadigan ayrim muammolarning oldini olish uchun.

Uchinchidan, zamonaviy til (ingliz, nemis, frantsuz) larni tez va osonroq o'zlashtirish uchun.

Avvalambor shuni ta'kidlash lozimki, tilshunos olimlarning hisoblariga qaraganda, ingliz tilida eng ko'p qo'llaniladigan 20000 so'zning 10400 tasi lotin tili so'zlarining o'zigidan yasalgan, 2200 tasi yunoncha, 5400 tasi anglo-sakson tili mahsuli ekan.

Bundan ko'rinib turibdiki chet tilini o'rganuvchi mutaxassislar lotin tilini o'rganishlari zarurdir. Biz quyida lotincha –inglizcha –nemischa –frantsuzcha -o'zbekcha ayrim so'zlarning ekvivalentini e'tiboringizga havola etamiz va yuqoridagi fikrga ishonch hosil qilamiz.

Lotincha	Inglizcha	Nemischa	Frantsuzcha	O'zbekcha
agricola, ae, f	peasant	der Bauer	aricole, paysan. agriculture	dehqon, dehqonchilik
amica, ae, f	friend	das Freunt	ami, m	do'st
animalis, is, f	animal	das Tier	animal	hayvon
collega, ae, f	colleague	der Kollege	colleague; m	hamkasb
dens, ntis, f	tooth	der Zahn	dent; f	tish
elephantus, i, m	elephant	der Elefant	elephant, m	fil
femina, ae, f	woman	die Frau	femme	ayol
fructus, us, m	fruit	die Fruchte	fruit; m	meva
genus, eris, n	generation	die Generation	generation; f	nasl, jins
grammatica, ae, f	grammar	die Grammatik	grammaire	grammatika
gutta, ae, f	drop	der Tropfen	goutte; f	tomchi
herba, ae, f	greens	das Gras	herbe; f(bot)	o't, ko'kat
homo, inis, m	person	der Mensch	homme; m	odam
humanus, a, um	humanitarian	dei Menschlichkeit	humanite; f	insoniylik

imago, inis, f	image	das Bild	image; f	tasvir, surat
index, icis, m	index finger	der Zeigefinger	index; m	ko'rsatkich barmoq
inferior, ius	low	unter	inferieur	pastki
juilius, i, m	july	juli	juillet; m	iyul
leo, leonis, m	lion	der lowe	lion	sher, arslon
mons, montis, m	mountain	der berg	montagne; f, mont; m	tog', tepalik
natalis, e	born	geboren	naitre (tug'ilmoq)	tug'ulgan
nomen, inis, n	name	der Name	nom; m	ism, nom
odor, oris, m	smell	dei Rieche	odeur; f	hid
os, ossis, n	bone	der Knochen	os; m (anat)	suyak
parens, ntis, m, f	parents	die Eltern	parents; m, pl	ota-ona
patria, ae, f	motherland	der Vatersland	patrie; f	vatan
planta, ae, f	plant	das Gras	plante, f	o'simlik, ekin
quantum	when	wann	quant	qachon
repetitio, onis, f	repeat	wiederholen	repetitio; f	takrorlash
septimus, a, um	seventh	siebente	septieme	yettinchi
sol, solis, m	sun	die Schule	soleil; m	quyosh
terra, ae, f	earth	die Erde	terre; f	yer
thorax, acis, m	thorax	der Thorax	thorax; m	ko'krak qafasi
verbum, i, n	verb	das Verb	verbe; m	fe'l
vir, viri, m	man	der Mann	viril (kishi)	erkak kishi
vita, ae, f	life	das Leben	vie; f, vivant	hayot
vulnus, eris, n	wound	der wurm	ulcere (med)	yara, jarohat
nasus, i, m	nose	der Nase	nez (anat)	burun

Lotin tilining III turlanish Femininum rodiga mansub Nominativusda -o qo'shimchasi bilan tugaydigan otlar asosan, Genetivus Singularisda –onis qo'shimchasiga ega bo'ladi. Masalan:
palpatio, onis, f –paypaslash, negizi paltation;

injectio, onis, f –igna orqali dori yuborish, negizi injection;
curatio, onis, f –davolash, negizi curation;
auscultation, onis, f –eshitib ko’rish, negizi auscultation.

Ana endi lotin tili so’z negizi zamonaviy Yevropa tillarida deyarli bir hilda yozilishga ekanligini xohlangan til lug’atlarida ko’rishingiz mumkin. Bu yerda, hurmatli o’quvchida faqat o’sha tilning fonetikasidan ozroq xabardor bo’lishlikning o’zi yetarli bo’ladi. Demak, Siz o’rganayotgan tilingizning fonetuk bilimlarini qo’llab, lotin tili leksikasidan bimalol foydalanishingiz mumkin. Chunki, bunday holatlar ko’plab uchraydi.

XULOSA

Xulosa qilib shuni aytish mumkinki, lotin tilining ahamiyati va imkoniyati cheksizdir. O’ziga do’sat bo’lgan har bir yosh o’quvchi zamonaviy tillarni o’rganishda lotin tilidan foydalanishi maqsadga muvofiqdir.

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